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NEXT GENERATION SCIENCE CHALLENGES USING DIGITAL AND SOCIAL MEDIA TO MAKE SCIENCE EDUCATION AND CAREERS ATTRACTIVE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

Deliverable D2.5

Best Practice Report on Science and Educational Challenges

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1. Introduction

The SciChallenge research project investigates the use of student-generated content and contests for enhancing the motivation of young people to pursue science education and careers.

In 2015, Prof. Valentina Dagiene received the “*Best Practices in Education Award*”¹ for the development of the concept of Bebras challenge in computer science (“bebras” means “beaver” in Lithuanian.) In the context of presentation ceremony of “*Best Practices in Education Award*” at the 2015 European Computer Science Summit in Vienna (AT), Judith Bishop (Microsoft Research) said that “*Involving children in all aspects of computing early on is the best way to ensure that they will continue in the discipline as a career.*”

Regarding the contests for young people, Adam Ruben wrote in his article² “*A scientist goes to kindergarten*” (Science, Nov. 18, 2015) “*Those contests were an essential part of my identity, not because of an obnoxious need for external gratification, but because I enjoyed trying to win them. The nervousness, the studying, the problem solving, the anticipation at the awards ceremony—those qualities were fun to me.*”

In this document, we focus on challenges (that is, contests or competitions) for young people in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). The contests of our interest target pre-university students. While some of the contests require innovation and entrepreneurship talent, there are contests that address problem-solving skills in a particular subject (such as, mathematics). By studying the existing contests and interviewing knowledgeable persons, we aim at identifying some of the best practices in STEM contests for pre-university students.

We study the following ten STEM related contests for pre-university students,

- International Olympiads
- Beavers of Computer Science
- Intel International Science and Engineering Fair
- Intel Science Talent Search
- Siemens Competition in Math, Science and Technology
- Junior Science and Humanities Symposia
- International BioGENEius Challenge
- Conrad Spirit of Innovation Challenge
- Google Science Fair
- EU Contest for Young Scientists

We would like to clarify the following questions,

- How the contest tasks/challenges are defined?
- Is the contest conducted online or face-to-face?
- Is the contest single-stage or multi-stage?
- How the contestants are evaluated?
- Which kind of awards the contest winners get?

¹<http://www.informatics-europe.org/news-and-events/229-bebras-wins-informatics-europe-2015-best-practices-in-education-award.html>

² DOI: 10.1126/science.caredit.a1500264

The rest of this document is structured as follows. Section 2 describes our methodology, which is based on interviews of education experts and analysis of existing STEM contests. We discuss results of interviews and analyze a representative set of existing STEM contests in Section 3. Section 4 summarizes our findings.

2. Methodology

We have aggregated information about STEM contests in the following two deliverables,

- D2.2: Baseline Report on Participatory Science Challenges,
- D3.2: Stakeholder scoping study including experiences, and requirements.

Figure 1. Identifying best practices using interviews and existing STEM contests.

In this document, we identify some of the best practices in STEM contest organization, by

- 1) analyzing the interviews of teachers and experts in science education, and
- 2) systematic studying of a representative set of STEM contests.

A teacher in this context is a person that is actively involved in teaching students in pre-university education. Whereas, an expert is a person knowledgeable about science education that is not involved in teaching pre-university students.

For each contest that is included in our study, we highlight the following features,

- 1) type of challenge/task,
- 2) target group of participants,
- 3) administrative implementation aspects,
- 4) technical implementation aspects,
- 5) awards.

3. Best Practices

In this section, we aim at identifying some of the best practices with respect to STEM contests for pre-university students.

3.1. Interviews

We highlight opinions of interviewees with respect to the best practices in the context of STEM contests for young people. A general description of the scoping study is provided in D3.2, and here we focus on the following,

- 1) good practices in contest organization,
- 2) online and face-to-face contests,
- 3) “*perfect*” contest features.

3.1.1. Good practices in contest organization

Regarding the good practices in contest organization, interviewees stated that challenges should be appropriate (that is, “*not too hard, not too easy*”) for the target group. Project-type challenges are often preferred compared to assignment-type challenges. An interviewee believes that “*this creates a very strong ownership among the pupils/young people that is much broader in its potential for developing competencies for the future than closed scientific assignments are.*”

Working in a group is considered a relevant aspect of good contests to address social concerns. According to an interviewee “*even if STEM is the strongest element, social skills are also needed, good team work, management skills, planning.*” There are examples³ of contests that the whole class participates as a group and works together to solve a problem. As part of this kind of activity, children are able to express different talents in contrast to the usual school assignments.

It is important to organize the contest in cooperation with schools, teachers and the corresponding education authorities. An interviewee believes that “*the schools must see clear evidence that this is bringing positive energy and encouragement to both their students and teachers.*” If for instance, administrative persons at the state level recommend to schools to participate in the contest, it may help significantly to increase the overall number of participants. An interviewee states, “*it is important for the image of the schools to have good teams or contestants in those events.*”

Several interviewees emphasized the importance of organizing contests at multiple-stages. For instance, “*it is good to organize them in few stages – usually it is good to locate the first stage in schools, but next stage and final one in a university or other science organization.*”

For organizing a successful contest, it is considered also important to offer attractive awards. According to an interviewee “*exciting awards related to STEM should be given – like journey and visit of famous STEM laboratory, widely publicized results of winners and also non-winning contributions.*”

³ www.teknikattan.se

3.1.2. Should contests be online or face-to-face?

We have observed among the interviewees that there are pros and cons for both online and face-to-face contests. It is believed that online contests may help to increase the degree of participation in case of contests that are organized across a large geographical space. While an interviewee believes that online contests could help to attract “*shy people*” to participate in the contest, another interviewee states, “*in an online competition, you can meet more students but I’m not sure, how that it will get the kids to wanting to study STEM.*” Social aspects of contests are considered relevant and it is believed that these aspects are better addressed in face-to-face contests.

Several interviewees have proposed to combine features of online and face-to-face contests. This could be done in the context of a multi-stage contest. For instance, online contests could be used in the preliminary stages, and thereafter face-to-face contests would be used at the final stage. An interviewee states as follows, “*Human aspect of the competitions and events is very important. Often though, mixed approaches can give fine results. So online elements might be fine as part of a bigger scheme.*”

3.1.3. What makes a perfect contest?

In this section, we highlight some of the features of a perfect contest according to the opinions of interviewees. An interviewee believes that “*an ideal contest would allow to compete in teams AND individually.*” A perfect contest could include theoretical challenges (for instance, in the preliminary stages) and practical challenges (in the final stage).

Social aspects are considered a relevant part of a perfect contest. According to an interviewee, “*friendship and laughter are important, as well as to spend time together in the preparation, during the contests and afterwards.*” Furthermore, an interviewee states, “*if I were about to organize a STEM contest it would definitively be a fun and social event with elements of gamification.*”

Several interviewees pointed to International Olympiads in various subjects (such as, in mathematics, chemistry, or informatics) as examples of good practices or perfect contests. Furthermore, interviewees recommend for large-scale contests that involve many countries to organize a multi-stage contest.

3.1.4. Summary of best practices according to interviewees

Best practices according to interviewees
Choose appropriate theoretical and practical tasks/challenges
Cooperate closely with schools, teachers, and education authorities
Combine online and face-to-face contest features
Consider social aspects (team working, interactions among participants,..)
Allow group and individual participation
Organize a large-scale contest in multiple-stages; online preliminary stages, and a face-to-face final stage

Table 1: Summary of the best practices based on information obtained from interviews.

3.2. Existing STEM Contests

In this section, we discuss a representative set of major STEM contests. We provide a general description of participatory science challenges in D2.2. In this document, we highlight the following features of existing STEM contests: (1) type of challenge/task, (2) target group of participants, (3) administrative implementation aspects, (4) technical implementation aspects (for instance, use of social media), and (5) awards.

The following ten STEM related contests for pre-university students are considered in our study,

- 1) International Olympiads
- 2) Beavers of Computer Science
- 3) Intel International Science and Engineering Fair
- 4) Intel Science Talent Search
- 5) Siemens Competition in Math, Science and Technology
- 6) Junior Science and Humanities Symposia
- 7) International BioGENEius Challenge
- 8) Conrad Spirit of Innovation Challenge
- 9) Google Science Fair
- 10) EU Contest for Young Scientists

3.2.1. International Olympiads

International Olympiads are annual contests for secondary school students that focus on problem solving skills in various subjects including: astronomy, biology, chemistry, geography, mathematics, informatics, or physics.

The International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO⁴), which was first organized in Braşov (RO) 1959, is an annual world competition in mathematics for high school students. Participants from more than 100 countries from different continents compete by solving six mathematical problems within two consecutive days. Participants are challenged to solve three mathematical problems each day within four and half hours. A major aim of IMO is to challenge and discover talented young mathematicians.

Problem 6. The sequence a_1, a_2, \dots of integers satisfies the following conditions:

(i) $1 \leq a_j \leq 2015$ for all $j \geq 1$;

(ii) $k + a_k \neq \ell + a_\ell$ for all $1 \leq k < \ell$.

Prove that there exist two positive integers b and N such that

$$\left| \sum_{j=m+1}^n (a_j - b) \right| \leq 1007^2$$

for all integers m and n satisfying $n > m \geq N$.

Figure 2. An example of a mathematical problem at the IMO 2015.

Each country that is invited to participate in IMO may send up to six “contestants” and two team leaders. Contestants should be citizens or residents of the country that they represent and they are not supposed to be enrolled at university. Contestants should not exceed the age of 20. Each

⁴ <https://www.imo-official.org>

participating country submits up to six proposals for problems from various fields of pre-university mathematics. Each contestant may receive the mathematical problems in one or two languages and write the answers in her/his own language. Contestants are not allowed to use computing and communicating devices. They are also not supposed to use literature (books) during the contest. Contestants are ranked based on their individual results. The top contestants receive Gold, Silver, or Bronze medals.

The International Physics Olympiad (IPhO⁵), which was first organized in Warsaw (PL) in 1967, is an annual world competition in physics for high school students. The duration of competitions is two days: day one for theoretical problems, and the day two for experimental problems. Each day the competition lasts five hours. The aim of IPhO is to improve education of young people (that is, secondary schools students) in physics.

Each participating country sends up to five contestants and two team leaders to IPhO. Contestants should be secondary school students and are not allowed to be enrolled at university. The tasks for the contest are prepared usually by the host country. Contestants are allowed to use only drawing instruments and non-programmable pocket calculators. Based on the individual results, approximately 8% of contestants receive a Gold medal; 25% of the contestants receive Gold or Silver; 50% of the contestants receive Gold, Silver or Bronze medal.

The International Chemistry Olympiad (IChO⁶), which was first organized in Prague (CZ) in 1968, is an annual world competition in chemistry for high school students. The contest involves a theoretical part (60 points) and a practical part (40 points). The contest aims at enhancing activities of students with creative and autonomous solutions of problems in chemistry. The participants receive the problem description in the language of their choice. The use of personal computing and communicating devices is not allowed.

Each participating country sends four contestants and two mentors to IChO. Usually a country selects competitors via regional and national competitions. Some countries organize also specific training sessions for their students that will participate in the Olympiad. Contestants should be students of secondary school that have not exceeded the age of 20 and should hold the passport of the country that they represent. The International Jury consists of the chair and several jury members. The chair of the International Jury is proposed by the organizer. Two mentors from the country delegations serve also as members of the International Jury. All students receive a certificate of participation. Depending on results, approximately 10% of students receive the Gold medal, 20% the Silver medal, and 30% the Bronze medal. Students are evaluated individually and they consequently receive awards individually.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	A set of theoretical and practical problems defined by the contest organizers.
Target group of participants	Secondary school students under the age of 20.

⁵ <http://www.jyu.fi/tdk/kastdk/olympiads/>

⁶ <http://www.ichosc.org>

Administrative implementation aspects	Each country is represented by (depending on the type of Olympiad) 4 – 6 contestants. Typically, the Olympiad is organized as a multi-stage contest. Countries may organize regional and national contests to select their contestants. Experts evaluate the solutions of contestants.
Technical implementation aspects	Contestants are not allowed to use advanced computing and communicating devices. Technologies such as social media are not used for evaluation of results.
Awards	Top ranked contestants receive Gold, Silver, or Bronze medals based on their individual results. There are no team awards.

Table 2: Features of International Olympiads.

3.2.2. Beavers of Computer Science

The challenge “Biber der Informatik” (in English “Beavers of Computer Science”) is organized annually by the Austrian Computer Society and aims at introducing the students of age 8 – 20 to Computational Thinking. There are five age subgroups for contestants: (1) 3rd and 4th grade, (2) 5th and 6th grade, (3) 7th and 8th grade, (4) 9th and 10th grade, (5) 11th – 13th grade. It is possible to participate in the competition individually or as a team of two members. The Beavers competition is organized online⁷.

For each school there is one teacher serving as coordinator, and registers the interested students. There are several multiple-choice tasks and contestants should click (that is, select) the right answer. The questions have the form of riddles. The tasks can be solved by thinking and no specific computer science knowledge is necessary. Duration of the competition is about 40 minutes and contestants should be under the supervision at school in this period. Results of the contestants are published online in anonymous form. The names of contestants are published only after the consent of parents has been received.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Multiple-choice questions; the right answer brings positive points, whereas the wrong answer results with negative points.
Target group of participants	Age 8 – 20
Administrative implementation aspects	Single-stage competition
Technical implementation aspects	Online competition
Awards	Anonymized ranking of the best contestants is public

Table 3: Features of Beavers of Computer Science.

⁷ <http://wettbewerb.biber.ocg.at>

Figure 3: Bebras task example.

The concept of Bebras⁸ challenge in Computational Thinking (“bebras” means “beaver” in Lithuanian) was developed by Prof. Valentina Dagiene at the University of Vilnius in Lithuania. The first Bebras challenge was organized in Lithuania in the year 2004. More than 1 300 000 contestants from 35 countries participated in the Bebras challenge in 2015. Prof. Dagiene received for the Bebras challenge the “Best Practices in Education Award⁹” from the Informatics Europe in 2015. This award is sponsored by the Microsoft Research. “*Involving children in all aspects of computing early on is the best way to ensure that they will continue in the discipline as a career*”, said Judith Bishop (Microsoft Research) at the award presentation ceremony during the 2015 European Computer Science Summit in Vienna, Austria.

3.2.3. Intel International Science and Engineering Fair (Intel ISEF)

Intel ISEF¹⁰ is an international annual contest dedicated to high school students focused on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Around seven million contestants are involved in the contest every year. Intel ISEF is supported by the Society for Science & the Public (SSP). The contestants participate in local science contests in the first stage. Thereafter, around 1700 winners of preliminary contests are invited to participate in the final contest.

The experts, who often hold a PhD degree in the respective field, evaluate the projects of the contestants. Projects are evaluated using the following criteria: research question/problem, design and methodology, execution, creativity, and presentation. The emphasis during the evaluation is on creativity and presentation.

⁸ <http://www.bebbras.org>

⁹ <http://www.informatics-europe.org/news-and-events/229-bebbras-wins-informatics-europe-2015-best-practices-in-education-award.html>

¹⁰ <https://student.societyforscience.org/intel-isef>

Project categories include: Animal Sciences (ANIM), Behavioral and Social Sciences (BEHA), Biochemistry (BCHM), Biomedical and Health Sciences (BMED), Biomedical Engineering (ENBM), Cellular and Molecular Biology (CELL), Chemistry (CHEM), Computational Biology and Bioinformatics (CBIO), Earth and Environmental Sciences (EAEV), Embedded Systems (EBED), Energy - Chemical (EGCH), Energy - Physical (EGPH), Engineering Mechanics (ENMC), Environmental Engineering (ENEV), Materials Science (MATS), Mathematics (MATH), Microbiology (MCRO), Physics and Astronomy (PHYS), Plant Sciences (PLNT), Robotics and Intelligent Machines (ROBO), Systems Software (SOFT), Translational Medical Science (TMED). Each of these categories includes sub-categories as well.

More than \$5 million worth awards and scholarships are available for contestants. The Gordon E. Moore Award (\$75000) is awarded to the contest winner. The next two positions win the Intel Foundation Young Scientists Award (\$50000).

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Any project defined by contestants that fits in one of the predefined categories.
Target group of participants	Secondary school students (grades 9 – 12, below the age 20).
Administrative implementation aspects	A multi-stage contest at local, national, and international level; teams of up to three members may compete; experts evaluate the projects of contestants.
Technical implementation aspects	Social media is not used for project evaluation.
Awards	The top award is worth \$75000, the next two are \$50000 each. Numerous additional awards (such as the attendance of the Nobel Prize ceremony in Stockholm (SE)) are available as well.

Table 4: Features of Intel ISEF.

3.2.4. Intel Science Talent Search (Intel STS)

Intel STS¹¹ that is supported by the Society for Science & the Public is a science contest for high school students in USA. It is organized as a multi-stage contest. Usually about 1800 contestants participate in the contest. After the preliminary stage of contest, the number of contestants is reduced to 300 semi-finalists. Each school receives \$1000 for each of its semi-finalists. The work of contestants is evaluated by the Ph.D. level scientists. Thereafter, the top 40 contestants are invited to Washington D.C. in the final stage contest. Finalists present their research results to the visitors and conduct interviews with the judging panel that consists of 15 scientists.

The contestants in the preliminary stage select one of the following categories: Animal Sciences (AS), Behavioral and Social Sciences (BE), Biochemistry (BI), Bioengineering (BN), Cellular and Molecular Biology (CM), Chemistry (CH), Computer Science (CS), Computational Biology and Bioinformatics (CB), Earth and Planetary Science (EP), Engineering (EN), Environmental Science (EV), Genomics (GE),

¹¹ <http://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/education/competitions/science-talent-search.html>

Mathematics (MA), Medicine and Health (ME), Materials Science (MS), Physics (PH), Plant Sciences (PS), Space Science (SS).

The contestants in the final stage compete in three major categories: basic research, global good, and innovation. In each major category, the winner receives \$150000, the second position is worth \$75000, and \$35000 is dedicated to the third position. Everyone else that participated in the final stage of the contest receives \$7500. Furthermore, all contestants in the final stage receive a paid trip to Washington D.C. It is worth to mention that eight former Intel STS contestants have received the Nobel Prize.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Any project of contestants that fits in one of the predefined categories.
Target group of participants	12 th grade of secondary school; USA citizens.
Administrative implementation aspects	Multi-stage contest; individual participation; results of contestants are evaluated by scientists.
Technical implementation aspects	Social media is not used for project evaluation.
Awards	For each of the three major categories (basic research, global good, and innovation): \$150000 for the 1 st position, \$75000 for the 2 nd position, and \$35000 for the 3 rd position.

Table 5: Features of Intel STS.

3.2.5. Siemens Competition in Math, Science and Technology

The Siemens Competition is dedicated to high school students (grades 9 – 12) that are citizens or permanent residents of the USA. Projects may be submitted by individual contestants or by a team of maximum three members. Projects of individual contestants are evaluated separately from the team projects. The Siemens Competition comprises six regional competitions and one national competition. Individual winners and team winners of the six regional competitions are qualified for competition at the national level. Contestants are evaluated based on the research report, the poster, the 12-minute presentation, and answers to the questions of a panel of judges. Teamwork is a specific evaluation criterion for projects submitted by a team of contestants.

Eligible project topics include: Astrophysics, Biochemistry, Bioengineering, Biology, Biophysics, Botany, Cell/Cancer Biology, Chemical Engineering, Chemistry, Civil Engineering, Computer Science, Earth and Atmospheric Science, Electrical Engineering, Environmental Science and Engineering, Genetics, Geology, Immunology/Virology, Materials Science/Nanoscience, Mathematics, Mechanical Engineering, Microbiology, Nutritional Science, Physics, and Toxicology.

The individual winner of one of the six regional competitions receives \$3000, whereas the winning team gets \$6000. Individual contestants and teams at the national level get for the first place \$100000, for the second place \$50000, for the third place \$40000, for the fourth place \$30000, for the fifth place \$20000, and for the sixth place \$10000.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Any project of contestants that fits in one of the predefined topics.
Target group of participants	High school students (grades 9 – 12) in USA.
Administrative implementation aspects	Multi-stage contest; winners of six regional competitions participate in the national competition. Individual and team participation is possible, and they are evaluated separately. A panel of judges evaluates contestants.
Technical implementation aspects	Social media is not used for project evaluation.
Awards	The top six individuals and teams at the national level receive \$100000, \$50000, \$40000, \$30000, \$20000, \$10000 respectively.

Table 6: Features of Siemens Competition.

3.2.6. Junior Science and Humanities Symposia (JSHS)

JSHS¹² is a competition for secondary school students in science, technology, engineering and mathematics. The competition is supported by the Department of Defense and by universities in the USA. The 48 regional competitions organized by universities reach an estimated 10000 secondary school students and teachers. Five contestants at each of the 48 regional competitions get the opportunity and financial support to travel to the national JSHS competition. At the regional competition, contestants present orally their research project to a panel of judges and to their peers.

Members of the judging panel are active researchers and typically hold a PhD degree. The contestants compete in the following eight major categories: Environmental Science, Biomedical Sciences, Life Sciences, Medicine & Health, Engineering and Technology, Math and Computer Science, Physics, and Chemistry. The research work done as a part of a team project is eligible, but the individual contribution of the contestant must be clearly identified. A contestant submits a research paper between 5 and 20 pages. At the national level, the research presentation is limited to 12 minutes.

Awards at the national level include: eight \$12000 tuition scholarships for the 1st place in one the eight categories, eight \$8000 tuition scholarships for the 2nd place in one the eight categories, and eight \$4000 tuition scholarships for the 3rd place in one the eight categories.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Any project defined by contestants that fits in one of the predefined categories.
Target group of participants	Secondary school students (grades 9 – 12); citizens or permanent residents of USA.

¹² <http://www.jshs.org/>

Administrative implementation aspects	Multi stage competition; 48 regional competitions and one national competition. A judging panel evaluates the contestants based on a 12-minute presentation and the research paper.
Technical implementation aspects	Social media is not used for project evaluation.
Awards	Tuition scholarships: \$12000 for the 1 st place, \$8000 for the 2 nd place, \$4000 for the 3 rd place.

Table 7: Features of JSHS.

3.2.7. International BioGENEius Challenge

The BioGENEius competition is dedicated to secondary school students (grade 9 -- 12) in Canada, Germany and USA. The projects of the contestants must be related to the biotechnology. Individual participation in the competition is eligible. Contestants are evaluated by a panel of experts. During the evaluation are considered the quality of the poster, the presentation and answers to the questions.

The contestants may address one of the following three major challenges in biotechnology: Global Healthcare Challenge, Global Sustainability Challenge, and Global Environment Challenge. The competition is organized at multiple stages: local, national, and international. Awards for the local challenge include: \$2000 for the 1st place, \$1000 for the 2nd place, and \$500 for the third place. The winner of the international challenge receives \$7500.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Projects with application to biotechnology.
Target group of participants	Secondary school students (grade 9 -- 12) in Canada, Germany and USA
Administrative implementation aspects	A multi-stage competition at local, national and international level. Projects are evaluated by a panel of experts.
Technical implementation aspects	Social media is not used for project evaluation.
Awards	\$7500 for the winner of international challenge.

Table 8: Features of BioGENEius Challenge.

3.2.8. Conrad Spirit of Innovation Challenge

The Conrad challenge is an annual competition for secondary school students. The contest is named after Apollo 12 astronaut Charles "Pete" Conrad Jr. Contestants address four major categories: Aerospace and Aviation, Energy and Environment, Cyber Technology and Security, and Health and Nutrition. Teams of two to five members (age 13 – 18) are eligible for participation. Each team has a coach/supervisor.

The team projects are first submitted to the contest portal. Each team describes textually their innovative idea and develops a video of up to three minutes duration. The team provides a link to

their video in YouTube or Vimeo. The Conrad Foundation recommends to all teams to consider filing a patent application before submitting their innovative idea to the contest portal.

The entry round and the semi-final rounds of the contest are conducted online. In the semi-final round, the top-scoring teams should submit a prototype or a proof of concept of their idea. Thereafter, the qualified contestants are invited in the final stage of the contest to personally present their projects to a panel of judges at the Kennedy Space Center Visitors Complex. The winners of the contest are honored as Pete Conrad Scholars and they may receive from sponsors funding support and guidance with respect to the intellectual property.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Any project idea that fits in the four predefined categories.
Target group of participants	Secondary school students of the age 13 – 18
Administrative implementation aspects	A multi-stage competition. A panel of experts evaluates the projects.
Technical implementation aspects	Preliminary stages are conducted online. The final stage is a face-to-face competition.
Awards	The winning teams are honored as Pete Conrad Scholars

Table 9: Features of Conrad Spirit of Innovation Challenge.

3.2.9. Google Science Fair

The Google Science Fair is an international competition in science and engineering. Eligible for participation are individuals and teams of up to three persons in the age range 13 – 18. The competition is organized online and for registration, a Google account is required. The contestants are divided in two age groups: age 13 – 15, and age 16 – 18. The consent of parents or legal guardian is required for participation.

There are two major project categories: *experimenting* and *engineering*. Following topics are eligible: Flora & Fauna, Food Science, Earth & Environmental Sciences, Inventions & Innovation, Electricity & Electronics, Robotics, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Behavioral & Social Sciences, Energy & Space, Astrophysics, and Computer Science & Math. Beside the project description, contestants may submit optionally a two-minute YouTube video or a slideshow with up to 20 Google slides. Contestants may use one of the following languages: English, German, Italian, Spanish, French, Arabic, Hebrew, Polish, Japanese, Russian, Turkish, Portuguese, Korean, or Chinese. Participants are divided in three geographic regions: (1) the Americas; (2) Europe, Africa & Middle East; (3) Asia, Pacific & Japan.

Sixteen Global Finalists get the opportunity to participate in the final winner selection event at the Google Headquarters in Mountain View, CA, USA. The judging panel selects four global finalists for each age group (13 to 15, and 16 to 18) and each category (experimenting and engineering) from a pool of the top 100 regional finalists.

The award for the Grand Prize Winner is a \$50000 scholarship from Google. All sixteen Global Finalists get a National Geographic subscription (12 months) and a Scientific American subscription (12 months). In addition, there are awards sponsored by LEGO and Virgin Galactic.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	Projects of contestants that fit one of the predefined categories and topics.
Target group of participants	Age 13 – 18.
Administrative implementation aspects	A multi-stage competition at regional and global level. Projects are evaluated by a judging panel.
Technical implementation aspects	Online competition. Only the sixteen global finalists are invited to a face-to-face meeting.
Awards	The major award is a \$50000 scholarship from Google

Table 10: Features of Google Science Fair.

3.2.10. EU Contest for Young Scientists

The European Union contest for young scientists EUCYS¹³ aims at helping young people in pursuit of a career in science and technology. EUCYS is an annual competition for young scientists, which is co-funded in the context of the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation “Horizon 2020.”¹⁴

Contestants of the age from 14 to 21 participate in the competition by submitting a technical report (up to 10 pages). A country may submit up to three projects from any field of science. The contestants set up a stand (see Figure 4) using their display materials (posters, demonstration prototypes, videos). During the Science Exhibition, the scientific jury evaluates them.

Figure 4: EUCYS 2015 (© European Union)

¹³ <http://www.eucys2015.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/>

Projects of individual contestants or teams of up to three members in any of the official languages of the EU are eligible. The jury of the corresponding national contest nominates contestants for EUCYS; it is assumed that the nominated contestants are the winners of the 1st prize in the national contest.

Major awards at EUCYS 2015 were as follows: three 1st prizes of €7000, three 2nd prizes of €5000 and three 3rd prizes of €3500. Three projects got the opportunity to participate in Intel ISEF. Furthermore, several European scientific organizations (such as CERN, EMBL, ESO) offer study visits of one week to successful contestants.

Feature	Description
Type of challenge/task	A project in any field of science.
Target group of participants	Age 14 to 21
Administrative implementation aspects	A multi-stage competition at national and international level. Projects are evaluated by a scientific jury.
Technical implementation aspects	Face to face competition.
Awards	€7000, €5000, and €3500 for the 1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd prize respectively.

Table 11: Features of EU Contest for Young Scientists.

4. Summary

We have studied best practices in STEM contests by analyzing interviews of knowledgeable persons in science education and existing STEM related contests. Some of the existing contests have a long tradition that enables to infer about the possible influence of the contests on future career path of participants. For instance, eight former Intel STS contestants have received the Nobel Prize.

How the contest tasks/challenges are defined?

There are two approaches to definition of tasks in the existing contests: (1) precisely defined problems or questions that contestants have to solve or answer, (2) broad categories or topics that contestants can choose to develop their projects. For instance, International Olympiads have a set of precisely defined problems (see Figure 2) that the contestants have to solve. Beavers of Computer Science uses for evaluation of the contestants multiple choice questions with four possible answers and the task of the contestants is to select the right answer. Science and engineering fairs usually define categories or topics that the contestants have to address in their projects.

Is the contest conducted online or face-to-face?

Beavers of Computer Science is completely conducted online. This approach is suitable for competitions with a large number of participants. For instance, more than 1 300 000 contestants from 35 countries participated in the Beavers challenge in 2015. International Olympiads may be considered face-to-face competitions in the sense that all contestants meet at a specific location and solve the problems under the supervision. Many science and engineering fairs combine online and face-to-face styles of competition. Online competition is used for the preliminary stages of the competition, and the finalists are invited to a face-to-face competition.

Is the contest single-stage or multi-stage?

Most of the existing competitions are multi-stage. They are organized at regional, national and international level. The winners of the lower stage proceed to the higher stage of the competition. The Beavers challenge may be considered as a single-stage competition.

How the contestants are evaluated?

In the context of competitions with precisely defined problems or questions, the evaluation of contestants is straightforward: the solution provided by the contestant is compared to the expected result. Evaluation of the projects of science and engineering fairs tend to be more complex. Contestants describe their projects with multiple artefacts: technical report (up to 20 pages), presentation slides, YouTube video, demonstration prototypes. In addition, in the final stage the contestants have to answer questions of the evaluation jury.

Which kind of awards the contest winners get?

Medals and monetary awards are common. For instance, Intel STS awards \$150000 for the 1st position, \$75000 for the 2nd position, and \$35000 for the 3rd position. The major award of the Google Science Fair is a \$50000 scholarship from Google. Beside monetary awards, study visits at prestigious scientific organizations (such as CERN, EMBL, ESO) are offered to successful contestants. Intel ISEF offers to successful constants the attendance of the Nobel Prize ceremony in Stockholm (SE). The Conrad Spirit of Innovation Challenge offers support and guidance with respect to the intellectual property.

5. Literature

Bell, D. & Jarman, N. (2014), *Presenting Computer Science Concepts to High School Students*. In: Olympiads in Informatics, Vol. 8, pp. 3–19.

Betts, J. N. (2014), *Evaluation of a High School Science Fair Program for promoting Successful Inquiry-based Learning*, Portland State University.

Combéfis, W. (2014), *Programming Trainings and Informatics Teaching Through Online Contests*. In: Olympiads in Informatics, Vol. 8, pp. 21-34.

Cuba-Ricardo, G.; Leyva-Figueroa, A. & Mendoza-Tauler, L. (2014), *Learning Strategies of Informatics Contestants*. In: Olympiads in Informatics, Vol. 8.

Ruben, A. (2015), *A scientist goes to kindergarten*, Science, Nov. 18, 2015, American Association for the Advancement of Science. DOI: 10.1126/science.caredit.a1500264

Yasar, S. & Baker, D. (2003), *The Impact of Involvement in a Science Fair on Seventh Grade Students*, Arizona State University.

Zaidieh, A. (2012), *The Use of Social Networking in Education: Challenges and Opportunities*. In: World of Computer Science and Information Technology Journal, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 18-21.

Online Sources:

- Beavers of Computer Science,
<http://www.ocg.at/de/biber-der-informatik>
- Bebras Challenge
<http://www.bebas.org>
- Conrad Spirit of Innovation Challenge,
<http://www.conradchallenge.org/>
- EU Contest for Young Scientists,
http://ec.europa.eu/research/eucys/index_en.cfm
- Google Impact Challenge,
<http://www.google.org/local-giving/impact-challenge/>
- Google Science Fair,
<https://www.google-sciencefair.com/en/>
- International Astronomy Olympiad (IAO),
<http://www.issp.ac.ru/iao/>
- International Biology Olympiad (IBO),
<http://www.ibo-info.org/>
- International Chemistry Olympiad (IChO),
<http://www.ichosc.org>

- International Geography Olympiad (IGEO),
<http://www.geoolympiad.org/>
- International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO),
<https://www.imo-official.org>
- International Olympiad in Informatics (IOI),
<http://www.ioinformatics.org>
- International Physics Olympiad (IPhO),
<http://www.jyu.fi/tdk/kastdk/olympiads/>
- Intel International Science and Engineering Fair,
<http://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/education/competitions/international-science-and-engineering-fair.html>
- Intel Science Talent Search,
<http://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/education/competitions/science-talent-search.html>
- International BioGENEius Challenge,
<http://www.biotechinstitute.org/>
- Junior Science and Humanities Symposia (JSHS),
<http://www.jshs.org/>
- Overview of the Top Science Competitions,
http://www.sciencebuddies.org/science-fair-projects/top_science-fair_overview.shtml
- Siemens Competition in Math, Science & Technology,
<https://siemenscompetition.discoveryeducation.com/?CFID=3882949&CFTOKEN=89a8a4c599756a78-95C5EBD5-91EA-44D4-24EB28D588724864>
- Society for Science & the Public (SSP),
<https://www.societyforscience.org/>

6. Glossary

- CERN: European Organization for Nuclear Research
- EMBL: European Molecular Biology Laboratory
- ESO: European Southern Observatory
- EUCYS: European Union contest for young scientists
- IAO: International Astronomy Olympiad
- IBO: International Biology Olympiad
- IChO: International Chemistry Olympiad
- IGEO: International Geography Olympiad
- IMO: International Mathematical Olympiad
- IOI: International Olympiad in Informatics
- IPhO: International Physics Olympiad
- ISEF: International Science and Engineering Fair
- JSHS: Junior Science and Humanities Symposia
- SSP: Society for Science & the Public
- STS: Science Talent Search
- STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics